

Supplementary materials

Figure S1 **A)** After polymerization TF was mounted on a motorized translational stage to control the immersion in the etchant solutions, stopping when the second resist mask was partially immersed. **B)** *top* TF after gold wet-etching and *bottom* chromium wet-etching.

Figure S2 Dielectric region on metal-coated TF obtained by FIB milling. The process involves milling one face at a time, rotating the fiber 90 degrees before each milling.

Figure S3 Selective emission from W2 as the input angle changes. Thanks to the possibility of using low-NA TPL to achieve extended dielectric apertures while preserving silica properties, modal selectivity is distinguished within the sections uncovered by the metal

Figure S4 Schematic representation of the analytical procedure followed to calculate the collection volume from iso-intensity lines. Based on the Pappus-Guldin theorem we calculated the volume of rotational solids by multiplying the area enclosed by the iso-intensity lines (yellow area) by the distance between the barycenter of the iso-surfaces and the optical axis of the fiber (d) by the angle of rotation.